

CODECHECK certificate 2024-021

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14236507>

Item	Value
Title	Using Consumer Wearables to Measure Physical Activity of Nursing Home Residents with Dementia
Authors	Daniela Gawehns
Reference	https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/mqg86
Codechecker	Tina Rozsos
Date of check	2024-11-28 16:00:00
Summary	Downloaded the aggregate data and ran R script to reproduce figures.
Repository	https://github.com/codecheckers/DementiaPhysicalActivity

Table 1: CODECHECK summary

Output	Comment	Size (b)
BoxplotallCatsMedIoPercent.pdf	manuscript Figure 1	5380
BoxplotallCatsSamsungPercent.pdf	manuscript Figure 2	5334
CorrelationMatrix_5sec_hc.tif	manuscript Figure 3	13230192

Table 2: Summary of output files generated

Summary

Successful CODECHECK. Executing the file `PlottingScripts.R` produces three figures that are equivalent to the ones present in the paper. See CODECHECKER notes for details.

CODECHECKER notes

Code was written in R. Running the the R script `PlottingScripts.R` yields all necessary output files. This took 1 minute to complete on a Windows 10 laptop with RStudio. On Linux Fedora, we received an error that we are not allowed to run the script in R, but the reason is unclear. This is likely due an issue with the Linux installation, not the code.

The `PlottingScripts.R` file contained all code required to produce a version of the three figures in the paper. There were some initial issues with the raw data files not being available in the GitHub repository. One of the authors of the paper (Daniela Gawehns) provided aggregate data, and edited the R script to remove any code dependent on the raw data.

With the aggregate data and edited script, we were able to create a version of all three figures present in the paper on three different Windows machines. The third figure contained the same statistics, but a different layout than the figure present in the paper. This is because the author updated the design of this figure for the paper that is currently in press, but has not updated the ArXiv version of the paper.

Recommendations

We suggest to the authors to consider the following suggestions for their next publication or workflow:

- make sure to include all necessary files in the repository upon submission, including aggregate data files
- use a folder structure to separate ‘read only’ files (such as data) from scripts (such as data pre-processing) and ‘write’ files (such as output files)
- further organize the GitHub repository (e.g. use `main` as the default branch, add a license, add a step-by-step reproduction guide in the README file)

Manifest files

BoxplotallCatsMedloPercent.pdf

Comment: manuscript Figure 1

Comment: manuscript Figure 2

CorrelationMatrix_5sec_hc.tif

Cannot include output file as figure.

Manually added files

```
grid::grid.raster(tiff::readTIFF("../CorrelationMatrix_5sec_hc.tif"))
```


Acknowledgements

We would like to acknowledge NWO for funding the CHECK-NL project, and enabling the workshop at Rotterdam.

Citing this document

Tina Rozsos, Stijn Peeters, Hanne Oberman, Veerle van Harten (2024). CODECHECK Certificate 2024-021. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14236507>

About CODECHECK

This certificate confirms that the codechecker could independently reproduce the results of a computational analysis given the data and code from a third party. A CODECHECK does not check whether the original computation analysis is correct. However, as all materials required for the reproduction are freely available by following the links in this document, the reader can then study for themselves the code and data.

About this document

This document was created using R Markdown using the `codecheck` R package. `make codecheck.pdf` will regenerate the report file.

`sessionInfo()`

```
## R version 4.4.2 (2024-10-31 ucrt)
## Platform: x86_64-w64-mingw32/x64
## Running under: Windows 10 x64 (build 19045)
##
## Matrix products: default
##
##
## locale:
## [1] LC_COLLATE=Dutch_Netherlands.utf8
## [2] LC_CTYPE=Dutch_Netherlands.utf8
## [3] LC_MONETARY=Dutch_Netherlands.utf8
## [4] LC_NUMERIC=C
## [5] LC_TIME=Dutch_Netherlands.utf8
##
## time zone: Europe/Amsterdam
## tzcode source: internal
##
## attached base packages:
## [1] stats      graphics  grDevices  utils      datasets
## [6] methods   base
##
## other attached packages:
## [1] readr_2.1.5      tibble_3.2.1    xtable_1.8-4
## [4] yaml_2.3.8       rprojroot_2.0.4 knitr_1.49
## [7] codecheck_0.11.4 parsedate_1.3.1 R.cache_0.16.0
```

```

## [10] gh_1.4.0
##
## loaded via a namespace (and not attached):
## [1] xfun_0.49          rdflib_0.2.9      tzdb_0.4.0
## [4] vctrs_0.6.5       tools_4.4.2       generics_0.1.3
## [7] parallel_4.4.2    curl_5.2.1        fansi_1.0.5
## [10] pkgconfig_2.0.3   pdftools_3.4.1    R.oo_1.25.0
## [13] redland_1.0.17-18 assertthat_0.2.1  lifecycle_1.0.4
## [16] compiler_4.4.2    atom4R_0.3-3      stringr_1.5.1
## [19] tiff_0.1-12       keyring_1.3.2     htmltools_0.5.7
## [22] pillar_1.9.0      crayon_1.5.3      whisker_0.4.1
## [25] tidyr_1.3.1       R.utils_2.12.3    cachem_1.0.8
## [28] zen4R_0.10        tidyselect_1.2.1  zip_2.3.1
## [31] digest_0.6.31     stringi_1.7.12    dplyr_1.1.4
## [34] purrr_1.0.1       grid_4.4.2        fastmap_1.1.1
## [37] archive_1.1.7     cli_3.6.1         magrittr_2.0.3
## [40] XML_3.99-0.16     crul_1.4.2        utf8_1.2.4
## [43] osfr_0.2.9        withr_3.0.2       bit64_4.0.5
## [46] roxygen2_7.3.2    rmarkdown_2.29    httr_1.4.7
## [49] bit_4.0.5         qpdf_1.3.4        askpass_1.2.1
## [52] R.methodsS3_1.8.2 hms_1.1.3         memoise_2.0.1
## [55] evaluate_1.0.1    rlang_1.1.1       Rcpp_1.0.10
## [58] glue_1.6.2        httpcode_0.3.0    xml2_1.3.5
## [61] fauxpas_0.5.2     rorcid_0.7.0      rstudioapi_0.17.1
## [64] vroom_1.6.5       jsonlite_1.8.8    plyr_1.8.9
## [67] R6_2.5.1          fs_1.6.2

```